

Fabrication of IoT Enabled System for Patient Health Care

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Abstract - This IoT Enabled System for measuring the Patient Health related parameter is a personal care device that helps people to measure their heart rate in real time or record the heart rate for later study. A micro-controller unit is included to analyze the signals received from the patient body and for any anomaly the monitoring and indicating system displays the records along with an alarm. In this present work, the real-time values of the process parameters are recorded within a specific interval of time which can be set by the user. The recorded values of the process parameters related to health of the patient's condition are essentially used for future analysis and treatment of a specific patient. The incorporation of blood pressure indicating systems, and blood sugar monitoring system with annunciation systems enhances the present work applicability for domestic use as well as in large sectors like hospitals.

Keywords – IoT enabled system, Patient health care, body temperature, LM 35 sensor, heart rate, ECG.

1.0 Introduction

IoT Enabled System for Patient Health Care gives a wider spectrum to any intelligent medical tool concerning patient health condition monitoring and provides them with telemedicine from a particular location to other locations which are under the coverage of internet network. This intelligent system estimates multiple numbers of health-related parameters of a person at regular intervals and a huge data set recorded by this intelligent health care system is stored in a cloud environment. The health-related parameters include heartbeat, body temperature, and blood pressure recorded for monitoring the overall health condition of a patient. These data stored in using cloud environment are going to be very useful data for research in the medical field. This IoT enabled Smart system can record huge data. This Smart Medical Instrument transmits the health-related information which has been monitored and recorded to a health expert for rechecking its analysis and self-generated report if it senses any enormously abnormal critical value of any health parameter. It generates an alarm to alert the expert as well as the patient to an enormously abnormal change in any parameter related to the patient's health. Unlike the other available health monitoring devices in the market including smart-watches, fitness trackers, smart-phones, and expensive hospital equipment this system helps to supervise the patient remotely and provides telemedicine competence in presence of the supervision of Medical Experts. According to the received information, related to the health parameters, the health expert prescribes the medicine for the patient. For any emergency health condition of a patient, this system can take care of the patient remotely. In this device, a precision Integrated circuit-based temperature sensor along with a transmitter is incorporated to get a compatible health temperature signal, received from the patient body. The body temperature of a specific patient is recorded. The output signal of the temperature transmitter is received. The Output signal is measured in mV. This Health care device is interfaced with an onboard Microcontroller based Arduino Uno microcontroller unit. A regulated voltage of a positive 5Volt power supply unit is required to activate the

microcontroller-based circuit. The specific ground pin is connected to the common ground of the circuit. To monitor and record the Heart rate, the principle of pulse transduction is applied. A dedicated pulse transducer unit is incorporated to transduce the pulse of a particular patient. The mechanism of the reflection of light through IR and LDR couple is the working principle of the pulse transducer. The thumb is placed on the surface of the pulse transducer. It detects the instantaneous volume flow rate of blood and according to the volume flow rate, the transducer section generates the corresponding voltage following the variation of intensity of reflected light. According to the volume of blood inside the capillary blood vessels, the transducer produces majorly two different levels of voltages. During the interval of two consecutive heartbeats, the volume inside the capillary blood vessel is considerably low. In this situation, due to the reflected light, a level of voltage is observed at the output of the pulse transducer. The light reflected at the time of a heartbeat will be less compared to that of the time during the time interval between heartbeats as the volume inside the capillary vessels is lesser. At the time of heartbeat, another level of the output voltage is produced. The reflection of light occurs much more during the positive peak of the pulse compared to the reflected light during the elapse of two consecutive heartbeats. This variation in transmission and reflection of the light intensity is obtained in the form of a pulse. This output pulse internally is conditioned through the pulse transducer to measure heartbeat and then programmed accordingly to read as heartbeat count.

2.0 Block diagram:

Fig: 1 Block Diagram

2.1 On-board microcontroller unit:

ATmega328P is the onboard microcontroller chip present on the Arduino Uno Board and is used as the signal processing unit. This board is utilized here in this present work as a controller unit. This microcontroller unit is an open-source microcontroller unit. The Input/Output pins of this board are utilized here as per the requirement of this work. The analog Input pins are interfaced with the temperature transducer circuit. The output voltage pulse of the pulse sensor is connected to another Analog Input pin. This board comprises 14 numbers of digital Input/Output pins out of which six numbers of pins can generate PWM output and Six analog Input/Output pins are there. These pins are programmed in the Integrated Development Environment (IDE) of the Arduino. To interface with the Arduino IDE with the Microcontroller on board a type B PVC-made 1-meter micro-USB 2.0 cable is used here in this present work. In this present work, no external power supply is used as this is powered with the USB cable through the laptop as the voltage level is compatible with the need of this present work. ATmega328P based Arduino Uno board consists of its crystal oscillator along with serial communication and voltage regulator so in this work the external synchronization unit and adjustment circuit is not used. The Digital Input and Output Pins is existing on the board 14 in number out of which 6 numbers of the pin are provided as Pulse Width Modulated Output Pins.

The Specification of Arduino Uno Microcontroller Board:

1. Microcontroller model: ATmega328P Operating Voltage: 5V

2. Input Voltage Range: 7.0-12.0V.
3. Output Voltage Range is 6.0-20.0V.
4. Digital Input and Output Pins are here 14 in number, out of which 6 pins are provided as Pulse Width Modulated Output Pins.
5. Pulse Width Modulated Digital Input and Output Pins are 6 in number.
6. Analog Input Pins are 6 in number.
7. The direct Current per Input and Output Pin is 20.0 mA.
8. Direct Current for 3.30V Pin is 50 mA.
9. Flash Memory with 32 KB exists in the ATmega328P board and out of which 0.5 KB is used by the system boot loader.
10. SRAM of 2.0 KB exists in ATmega328P Microcontroller.
11. EEPROM is of 1.0 KB exists in ATmega328P Microcontroller.
12. The clock Speed is 16 MHz required.
13. LED_BUILTIN is available here in 13 numbers.
14. The length of the board is 68.5 mm.
15. The width of the board is 5834 mm.
16. The weight of the board is 24.90 g.

2.2 Temperature transducer unit:

An LM35 Integrated Circuit-based temperature transducer is designed to sense the temperature of the patient body. This parameter is a very important parameter to determine a patient's health condition. The fever causes due to any irregular functionality of different major organs within the human body. Even if there is any bacterial or fungal infection residing in any patient's body there is an abrupt change in body temperature occurs. So, this precision integrated-circuit temperature sensor as well as temperature transducers not only detects the temperature change but also transduces the patient's body temperature into an output voltage. From the observations, the character of the transducer may be drawn. The output voltage is linearly proportional to the change in the temperature on the scale of degree Celsius. This is also found that the temperature transducer Integrated Circuit LM35 shows an adequate range of linear temperature zone. On the other hand, other temperature sensors in the range of linear temperature mostly are calibrated in the temperature scale of degree Kelvin. So the Integrated Circuit LM35 has been chosen as the temperature transducer in this present work. The choice of this transducer for this present work makes the calibration of the temperature scale easier and more convenient. It is not required to adjust a large zero adjustment voltage from the output of the temperature transducer and a convenient Celsius scale may be easily obtained. This Integrated Circuit based temperature transducer LM35 provides an accuracy of ± 0.22 in Celsius scale in the ambient temperature surrounded by it. From the experimental observation, it is found that about ± 0.76 in Celsius scale over the full-scale temperature range of -55°C to $+150^{\circ}\text{C}$. This temperature transducer is chosen for this particular application due to its low cost, and market availability. This temperature transducer is also chosen due to its low output impedance, and output voltage range. There is no need for external calibration because the precise inherent calibration is there. The interfacing and controlling are done using the At mega microcontroller unit. Using a simple interfacing unit, recording unit, or control circuitry all the information on patient health parameters is recorded. The external power supply is not used but the microcontroller board uses the power unit of the Laptop itself in this present work. In the future, it may be replaced by a single regulated power supply unit of D.C. +9V as per the application need. It is the experimental observation is that the microcontroller board draws only $60\ \mu\text{A}$ D.C. current from its supply. As this device is of very low self-heating in nature and observed only less than 0.10°C in still air. From the experimental records regarding the huge temperature range starting from -55°C to $+150^{\circ}\text{C}$ this LM35 with -10°C with improved accuracy is chosen as the best fit for this specific application.

Specifications of the Temperature Transducer-LM35:

1. This device is directly calibrated in degree Centigrade.
2. It has a linearity of $+ 10.00\ \text{mV}/^{\circ}\text{C}$.
3. This device provides the 0.5°C accuracy at $+25^{\circ}\text{C}$ with the full-scale range -55°C to

+150°C

4. It is economical.
5. It Operates from 4.0V to 30.0V with a very minimum amount of current of 60 μ A.
6. It is a device with Low self-heating.
7. This device provides a low value of output impedance.

2.3 Pulse sensor unit:

This transducer follows the principle of a photo interrupter. It forms the photoplethysmography sensor. The device is chosen here the TCLR5000 as the pulse sensor. An infra-Red diode is coupled with a phototransistor in a single unit which makes a pulse sensing unit. The face of the Infra-Red diode and the phototransistor are exposed and the rest section is completely detached. When the patient places the thumb on the transducer surface, the instantaneous volumetric blood flow rate of the blood inside the thumb due to heartbeat varies. For this reason, the intensity of the reflected beam of light also changes. This change is detected and that indicates the heartbeat of the ill person. When much more intense light falls on the photosensitive transistor it conducts a higher range of current. The increased amount of the collector current of the photosensitive transistor decreases the collector voltage of the device and vice versa happens when less amount of light falls on the photosensitive transistor. This variation in the collector voltage is recorded and characterized as a variable that is dependent on the rate of change in the heart beat. To compensate for this variation, an additional signal conditioning circuit is introduced in this present work for proper interfacing with a microcontroller. A low pass filtration unit is added to remove the irregularities in the output.

Fig.2 Block diagram of the pulse sensing unit

Specification of the Pulse Sensor unit:

1. Diameter of this device is 0.6248 inches.
2. Overall thickness of the device is 0.12490 inches.
3. Working Voltage of this device is in the range of 3.0V to 5.0V.
4. Working Current of this sensor is near about in the range of 4.0mA at 5.0V.

2.4 Display unit-7 segment LED:

A 7-segment display unit of liquid crystal (LCD) is used in this present work as a local indicating unit. Lcd is chosen here due to its easy interfacing process with the present microcontroller unit. It is observed that LCD is of very low power consumption devices it is chosen for this present work.

2.5 Wi-Fi module-ESP8266:

The compact module of the nomenclature ESP8266 Wifi module is chosen as the communicating interface with the Blynk Application Server as the middle wire server. This low-cost Wifi module that belongs to ESP's family is chosen for this economic application. This device is used in this work to communicate with any place in the world in the cloud environment. This device has an in-built microcontroller with a flash memory unit. For this unit, the device is allowed to connect to Wi-Fi to make communication between the diseased person and the expert for telemedicine purposes. The Transmission Control Protocol and the Internet Protocol allow the module to communicate with Wi-Fi signals in the cloud server Environment. The working

voltage of this module is a 3.30 Volt maximum value. A voltage divider circuit is developed to drop a part of the supply voltage of 5volt and about 2.5 Volts is used here. The ESP8266 Integrated Circuit acts in this present work as an interpreter between the remote sensors and the cloud Server. Here an application middle wire is required to connect with the browser which usually transmits the requisite information to the second layer server.

Fig. 3 Diagram of working of ESP8266 as Interpreter between the remote sensors and the Server

ESP8266 section mentioned in the above figure is interfaced with the nearby Wi-Fi hotspot. This process allows the complete system to access the network and sends the requisite information to the Blynk Application Server. The Application server requires the authentication code which is to be delivered by the user. An authentication code is then transmitted to the application server which contains the same authentication code. If these two codes match that enables the procedure of data transmission to the main server through the Application server. The application server receives the code after which a secure connection is formed between the application server and the Wi-Fi module with part number ESP8266. To control the remote device and data transmission from it is initiated through the Blynk application and is sent to the Blynk Application server along with the authentication code. The ESP8266 module contains the same authentication code to connect with the Blynk server. The Application Server identifies the match with its code then only the information is sent to the corresponding ESP8266 module. Then respective microcontroller present in the ESP8266 turns ON the remote device.

3.0 Circuit diagram:

Fig. 4 Circuit Diagram

To build up the smart system, the development of hardware is the most crucial work. The core part of the device is the Arduino UNO which consists of an ATmega328P microcontroller. The output of the Heartbeat Sensor Module is coupled to the Analog Input Pin (Pin 1) of Arduino. The output of temperature sensor LM 35 is attached to the Analog Input Pin (Pin 2) of Arduino. These two parts act as the input to the system. The microcontroller processes the information and delivers output to the subsidiary devices, LCD, and ESP8266 Wi-fi module. The LCD displays the body temperature in Fahrenheit and the heart rate in BPM. The four data pins of the LCD Module (D4, D5, D6, and D7) are joined to the corresponding pin of the Arduino UNO onboard microcontroller unit. In this present work, a 10K Ω potentiometer is used for the adjustment of the display and here a satisfactory result has been achieved. Pins 3 and 5 of the LCD display unit are connected to the corresponding pins of the Arduino UNO on-board microcontroller unit. The Wi-fi module ESP8266 is linked to the output pin of the Arduino UNO. This Wi-Fi module acquires the information from the transducer and this received information is transmitted to the server. LED is connected as a local indicating device.

4.0 Algorithm of the software program:

Besides the hardware development, this project requires a strong software platform. Arduino Ide is used for this project where the language is C++. Through the Arduino compiler software, the program is executed. Using Thing Speak, the program is loaded into the microcontroller.

Steps to execute the program developed for this project are given below:

STEP 1: At first new projects are to be created.

STEP 2: As per the requirement new channel is to be created.

STEP 3: Then generate new API keys and set the data as per the requirement.

STEP 4: Then the program is to be uploaded in the Arduino UNO.

Step 5: Serial Monitor to be opened and it connects the system to Wi-Fi and other connected devices.

5.0 Record of Health Parameters:

Data streaming of developed IoT Enabled System for Patient Health Care using ESP8266 module & Arduino is mentioned below.

Fig. 5 Body temperature & Pulse rate metering with the Picture of the fabricated circuit

6.0 Conclusion:

Now IoT becomes an integral part of smart systems. The incorporation of IoT in the project enhanced the usability of the work. This device measures and monitor different health parameters like body temperature, and pulse rate remotely as well as patient can observe his/her health condition through a liquid crystal display. It helps elderly people and physically disabled people to get continuous health updates and medical assistance. Any emergency that arises during any time of day can be handled by medical officials immediately. Regular check up of patients suffering from certain diseases can be possible by this system, provided some extra features have been added to the project. The applicability of this work can be enhanced by incorporating some more sensors in the system to detect other health related parameters like blood pressure, SPO2, etc.

7.0 Application:

Besides continuous monitoring of a patient medical condition, this project also sends a notification to doctors and other people related to the medical fraternity through the mobile app. A bank of a medical database is formed and this database becomes a ready reference for the medical history of a patient. This data can be used for any medical research purpose. During pandemics or calamities, there is a dearth of medical staff. Online recording data can help to get rid of this situation by reducing the workload of medical staff.

8.0 References

1. Dikshit, K., & Prasad, S. K. (2021). Iot-based advanced smart patient monitoring system. In *Emerging Technologies in Data Mining and Information Security: Proceedings of IEMIS 2020, Volume 1* (pp. 935-942). Springer Singapore.
2. V. Balasubramaniam. (2020).IoT based biotelemetry for smart health care monitoring system. *Journal of Information Technology and Digital World*.
3. Valsalan, P., Baomar, T. A. B., & Baabood, A. H. O. (2020). IoT based health monitoring system. *Journal of critical reviews*, 7(4), 739-743.
4. Naik, B.N., Gupta, R., Singh, A. et al. (2020). Real-Time Smart Patient Monitoring and Assessment Amid COVID-19 Pandemic – an Alternative Approach to Remote Monitoring. *J Med Syst* 44, 131. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-020-01599-2>
5. Kharel, J., Reda, H. T., & Shin, S. Y. (2017). An architecture for smart health monitoring system based. *Journal of Communications*, 12(4), 228-233.
6. Krishnan, D. S. R., Gupta, S. C., & Choudhury, T. (2018, June). An IoT based patient health monitoring system. In *2018 international conference on advances in computing and communication engineering (ICACCE)* (pp. 01-07). IEEE.
7. Vaibhav, A., & Ahmad, I. (2018). IoT-Based Patient Health Monitoring System. In *Microelectronics, Electromagnetics and Telecommunications: Proceedings of ICMEET 2017* (pp. 177-183). Springer Singapore.
8. Ibrahim, A. A., & Zhuopeng, W. (2018). "IOT Patient Health Monitoring System. *Int. Journal of Engineering Research and Application* ISSN, 2248(9622), 01-03.
9. Karthik, B. N., Parameswari, L. D., Harshini, R., & Akshaya, A. (2018). Survey on IOT & Arduino based patient health monitoring system. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology*, 3(1), 1414-1417.
10. Rani, S. U., Ignatious, A., Hari, B. V., & Balavishnu, V. J. (2017). IoT patient health monitoring system. *Indian journal of public health research and development*, 8(4).